

Interwoven Realities: Integration and Identity in Multicultural Settings

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Abstract

The concepts of belonging, community, and integration are deeply interconnected, collectively shaping individuals' well-being, sense of comfort, and capacity to participate effectively in diverse social settings. This study explores these relationships through in-depth interviews with refugees, analysing their narratives to identify key factors that facilitate integration into host societies. The findings indicate that integration in Finland is accompanied by significant challenges, including language barriers, limited recognition of prior qualifications, and difficulties in building social and professional networks.

The research highlights the multifaceted nature of belonging, demonstrating how refugees and migrants actively construct identities and derive meaning within specific temporal and spatial contexts. By examining the interconnected narratives of belonging, community, and integration, the study provides nuanced insights into the processes that underpin successful refugee integration and underscores the importance of robust support systems in enabling this transition.

Methodologically, the study employs the Listening Guide (LG) approach, an analytical framework informed by psychology, human development, sociocultural studies, and literacy education. Through life story interviews, the research offers a rich understanding of how refugees navigate the complexities of integration, emphasising the central role of language as a foundational element of social cohesion and inclusion.

Introduction

The concept of *belonging* captures a sense of happiness, comfort, and feeling “at home” within a particular situation, while *community* is often understood as a broader social or societal context. *Integration*, by contrast, refers to the process through which different elements are brought together to function more effectively. Although these concepts are frequently discussed separately, they are deeply interconnected and collectively shape how individuals experience participation and meaning in social life. To explore these relationships, this study draws on interviews with refugees, analysing

their narratives to develop a cohesive understanding of belonging, community, and integration. Through this process, three core elements emerged as central to integration: acquisition of the host-country language, access to education, and engagement with cultural and social practices.

Definitions offered by the *Cambridge English Dictionary* describe belonging as feeling happy or comfortable in a situation, community as society in a general sense, and integration as the combination of elements to enhance effectiveness. While these definitions provide a useful starting point, this study moves beyond them by examining how these concepts are lived and negotiated in everyday life. Data were analysed using the Listening Guide (LG) method, a narrative and relational analytical approach grounded in psychology, human development, sociocultural studies, and literacy education (Woodcock, 2016). The LG method enables a multi-layered exploration of participants' voices and experiences, offering insight into both individual meaning-making and broader social contexts. Employing this narrative framework within a life story interview approach facilitated a nuanced examination of refugees' experiences of participation and integration.

For refugees, establishing meaningful connections to integration within an increasingly diverse world is critical. Integration is often framed in terms of employment and language acquisition, yet these processes depend heavily on the availability and effectiveness of sup-

port systems. Language, in particular, plays a foundational role in shaping and sustaining the social world, as emphasised by Gergen (2001) and Riessman (1993). At the same time, increased mobility within the European Union has transformed social and economic relationships, challenging traditional notions of belonging while simultaneously revitalising group identities (Marsh et al., 2007).

In the Finnish context, the pathway toward integration presents multiple challenges, including limited language proficiency, difficulties in recognising prior qualifications, restricted access to professional networks, and variability in the effectiveness of integration procedures. Despite these challenges, refugee integration can generate significant benefits across economic, social, educational, health, and cultural domains, contributing to broader freedoms within host societies (De Haas, 2005). Education emerges as a particularly critical factor, as many refugees arrive with interrupted or limited educational opportunities and encounter systemic barriers to the recognition of existing qualifications.

Exploring belonging, community, and integration through refugees' life stories allows for a deeper understanding of how these concepts intersect in practice. Belonging, in particular, lies at the heart of how individuals assign meaning to their lives (Ahmad, 2007, p. 7). Refugees' and migrants' experiences illustrate that belonging extends beyond formal inclusion or ethnic affiliation, encompassing emotional,

relational, and contextual dimensions (Ahmed, 2015, p. 54). Its significance lies in revealing how individuals construct and negotiate belonging within specific temporal and spatial contexts, operating simultaneously at micro and macro levels (Ahmed, 2012, 2015; Marsh et al., 2007).

The Role of Language in the Refugee Experience

Navigating life within societies characterised by diverse cultural backgrounds presents significant challenges. Across Europe, increasing cultural diversity has made language an indispensable tool for communication and dialogue. Within this multicultural landscape, language proficiency plays a central role in successful integration, particularly for refugees and migrants.

Learning the language of the host country represents a crucial entry point into integration processes. It not only facilitates social participation but also enables access to essential services, including healthcare systems within the host society. To explore this relationship in greater depth, this study employed the Voice-Centred Relational Method (VCRM), an analytical approach developed by Gilligan et al. (2003) as part of the Listening Guide (LG) framework.

The narratives shared by participants reveal profound struggles, especially among those with traumatic past experiences. For example,

one participant described experiencing educational deprivation due to familial circumstances and trauma, which significantly limited her ability to pursue education in Finland. Such accounts highlight the urgent need to increase awareness, support, and opportunities for resilience, particularly for refugee women navigating adversity within host societies.

“She was unable to attend school and instead remained at home, helping her mother with household chores. At a young age, she was forced into a marriage arranged by her family. After several years living in Kurdistan, Iran, the family was compelled to leave the country for safety reasons due to her husband’s political activities. They relocated to Iraq, where they lived for approximately fifteen years, moving between different locations within the country.

During this time, she cared for her children while her husband worked as a *peshmerga*. She was unable to read or write, and daily life was extremely challenging. Her husband later sustained a serious injury, and doctors informed him that he would no longer be able to drive. After the family resettled in Finland as refugees, he purchased a car to support the needs of their large family. Tragically, a few years later, he was involved in a car accident and died as a result of his injuries.

She was left as a single mother caring for eight children, an experience that constituted a pro-

found shock and trauma for both her and her family. Owing to the emotional and physical effects of this trauma, she was unable to pursue formal education in Finland. Instead, she devoted herself to raising her children, supporting their education, and helping them establish stable lives and successful careers.

Today, she owns a small garden where she grows vegetables and sells them within the Kurdish community. She now lives contentedly in Finland, spending much of her time with her grandchildren. Notably, she has also learned to drive, symbolising a significant transformation in her independence and life circumstances.”

(Narenj, 60-year-old woman)

Refugee women, despite their resilience in the face of adversity (Davis, 2000), often endure profoundly stressful migration journeys that significantly affect both their mental health and physical well-being, particularly when resettling in a new country and navigating an unfamiliar language (Miller et al., 2002). Dona and Berry (1999) demonstrate that language proficiency and formal education function as key competencies in enabling refugees to build stable and meaningful lives in their host societies.

The experiences of Kurdish women in refugee contexts offer a particularly powerful narrative, amplifying women’s voices while fostering empowerment within refugee communities.

Through sustained efforts to learn new languages, engage with diverse cultures, and pursue education, many Kurdish women have emerged as advocates for human rights, actively supporting other women facing displacement and marginalisation. In this context, language acquisition and education serve as critical tools through which refugee women can improve their socio-economic circumstances and respond to the complex demands of life in host countries (Chung et al., 1998).

These narratives frequently recount the painful departure from familiar homelands, marked by separation from family and friends and the experience of isolation and distress. Yet, even under such conditions, refugee women continue to learn, adapt, and contribute positively to their new societies. Their experiences embody ongoing struggles for dignity, freedom, and human rights, highlighting both vulnerability and strength in contemporary contexts of forced migration.

“I began attending Finnish language classes to learn the language and never gave up, committing myself to studying harder to integrate and become familiar with Finnish culture. My husband and I later started our own business, which further supported our integration.

Through my language studies, I interacted regularly with Finnish people, and this helped me feel more connected to Finnish society and culture. In turn, I also support Kurdish women in their efforts to in-

tegrate into Finnish society. My involvement in political activities allows me to make a meaningful contribution to the world around me. I want to continue helping Kurdish people build stable and fulfilling lives for themselves in Finland.”

(Shno, 37-year-old woman)

Linda Morrice, a senior lecturer at the University of Sussex, together with colleagues in geography and psychology, highlights the dual role of language as both a crucial facilitator and a potential barrier to individuals’ well-being and achievements. This perspective helps explain why many refugee communities place strong importance on acquiring a new language, recognising it as central to successful integration within the host society.

Despite the multiple challenges associated with migration, individuals often endure significant hardship while striving to maintain a strong sense of connection to their communities. Many actively seek to support newly arrived migrants by learning the host-country language and familiarising themselves with its cultural and social norms. Even when facing post-traumatic stress and severe physical disabilities, their resilience remains evident. Rather than allowing past suffering to define them, they transform painful experiences into sources of strength, fostering a deep belief in their own capacities and agency.

“I have always felt a strong connection to Kurdish culture and made conscious efforts to embrace and preserve it. For example, I actively advocated for

Kurdish rights in debates, wore Kurdish clothing whenever possible, and was generally known as someone with a strong sense of national identity.

At the same time, I enrolled in a language school as early as possible to learn Finnish. I believe I was able to integrate into Finnish society relatively quickly because I was committed to building a new life for myself and my family. Being a refugee is not easy, and others need to understand where we come from, as every country has its own challenges, and every individual carries their own experiences. I want to become more politically involved and help Kurdish people integrate more effectively into Finnish society.”

(Peshava, 40-year-old man)

Acquiring a new language is pivotal, as it opens access to information and enables the development of new experiences in unfamiliar settings. Language learning strengthens individuals’ capacity for autonomy and motivation within new cultural and societal contexts. The degree of engagement and its impact vary across studies, reflecting differences in learning environments and contextual conditions (Pablo et al., 2015).

Her journey was particularly challenging, as she had never anticipated leaving her homeland. Following her marriage, she and her husband left their hometown in search of a better life, relying on smugglers to reach another country. In this new environment, she encountered numerous hardships. Her narrative is significant from multiple perspectives, including its relevance to multicultural contexts, women’s rights—given the violations she experienced—

and the challenges posed by language barriers. At the same time, her story highlights remarkable resilience and growing awareness in confronting and navigating these intersecting difficulties.

“I moved to the north of Finland in September. After three years of drifting and feeling homeless, I felt stable for the first time and began to hope for a new start. I started learning the Finnish language, and I felt free and reborn.

Although language barriers remained and it was still difficult to integrate and fully understand Finnish culture, the course I attended helped me to better understand Finnish society and support my integration.

Finnish people often do not know what we go through.”

(Mahabad, 40-year-old woman)

Refugees frequently experience interruptions to their foundational education due to conflict and upheaval in their countries of origin, resulting in significant language barriers when resettling in host societies. A study conducted by the University of Sussex (2015) highlights how such educational disruption can hinder linguistic development and, consequently, the integration process. Successful integration is closely linked to a sense of belonging within the host community, which is strongly facilitated by language proficiency and opportunities for meaningful engagement.

Further research conducted in the United Kingdom emphasises the critical role of language in strengthening refugee resilience, not-

ing its importance in developing essential literacy skills and broader communicative competence (Sowton, 2016). Similarly, studies in Finland indicate that integration is a long-term and complex process in which learning the host-country language represents a foundational step. This research also stresses the need for diverse and culturally responsive educational approaches to bridge gaps between refugees' countries of origin and their new social environments (MacGilleon, 2017).

Understanding refugee integration is inherently complex and closely connected to refugees' social adaptability and capacity to navigate life in host societies. This multifaceted process requires coordinated professional expertise, educational support, and mental health awareness, underscoring the interdependence of language acquisition, social integration, and psychosocial well-being.

“We faced our first difficulties when adapting to a new country. It is always hard to move to a place where you cannot speak the language. Problems can feel like a vast sea, and to overcome them, you must learn how to swim. If you become a strong swimmer, you can cross the sea and succeed.

The first challenge is learning how to integrate into a new society. I learned to speak Finnish fluently and began working. At the same time, the host country must also make an effort and support people in adapting and integrating. I try to integrate into Finnish culture, but it is not easy, and my soul will always remain in Kurdistan.”

(Kamran, 56-year-old man)

Language is a fundamental medium for intercultural communication and a critical component of successful integration within host societies. Learning a new language is especially important, as it encourages openness to engaging with different cultures and social contexts. Through linguistic and cultural interaction, individuals can reshape their perspectives, attitudes, and worldviews, fostering a deeper sense of belonging within diverse societies. For refugees in particular, acquiring proficiency in the host-country language is pivotal to strengthening their integration and participation in everyday life (Muliro, 2019).

Integration plays a vital role in shaping cohesive societies and cultural interaction, underscoring the importance of belonging within refugee and migrant communities. Its impact extends beyond individual experiences, contributing to connections across ethnically diverse societies and cultures (Permoser & Rosenberger, 2012). The United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), through the 1951 Refugee Convention and the 1967 Protocol, highlights integration as a key mechanism for safeguarding refugees and enhancing their capacities within host countries. However, prolonged conflict in the Kurdistan region has significantly complicated the lives of many individuals, who often lack adequate international protection during forced displacement, resulting in persistent social, legal, and economic hardships.

“My first years in Finland were very difficult, and I often stayed at home with little to do. Over time, I learned how to cope with life in Finland. I recognise that there are cultural differences, but I have come to accept differences in religion, family life, and lifestyle. At the same time, Finnish society needs to reconsider its perceptions of refugees and offer greater support to help them cope and adapt more effectively.” (*Kaveh, 50-year-old man*)

The Kurdish community communicates through a range of dialects, reflecting strong bilingual or multilingual capacities and their adaptation within the countries in which they reside. Toivanen’s (2013) research on *Multilingual Performances of Belonging* highlights the linguistic diversity present among Kurdish migrant populations. Within Kurdish historical and cultural contexts, multilingualism has long been regarded as an integral component of identity, representing a valuable resource and a positive asset for the future integration of refugees in Finland.

Refugee integration is a complex and multifaceted process that often presents significant challenges when adapting to new cultures and societies. This process is closely intertwined with refugees’ lived experiences and their language proficiency in the host country. A sense of belonging to a community can intensify individuals’ feelings of responsibility and engagement. As Marsh et al. (2007) argue, belonging plays a central role in how people assign meaning to their lives, frequently grounded in shared ethnicity, histories, and experiences.

Integration, therefore, seeks to capture the evolving relationship between refugees' aspirations and their opportunities to pursue meaningful goals within the host society.

Many refugees, having been forced to flee their countries and rebuild their lives elsewhere, express feelings of disappointment and distress arising from experiences of control, discrimination, and the marginalisation of their rights and needs. Ongoing concerns about their own future and that of their families further compound these challenges, shaping both their integration trajectories and their sense of belonging in the host country.

"My generation needs to talk openly about the pain and difficulties we have experienced in the past to address them and move forward. I have tried to keep my cultural beliefs separate from my children's lives while adapting to a more European way of life. Above all, I want my children to have a normal life."

(Mustafa, 47-year-old man)

Kurds have historically lived within multicultural societies; however, their citizenship rights have often been marginalised or denied in these contexts. Many aspire to live in multicultural societies grounded in human rights and equality. Supporting the integration of migrants and refugees into new cultural contexts contributes to the development and strengthening of genuinely inclusive multicultural societies. Multiculturalism, which recognises and values cultural diversity, has gained prominence in recent decades for its role in promoting integration and advancing social equality. Within this

framework, acquiring linguistic and behavioural skills, alongside new forms of knowledge, is essential for effective communication and meaningful participation in community life (Ozkirimli, 2013).

Parekh (2000) argues that a cohesive and stable multicultural society is both possible and desirable. Similarly, Hickmann et al., (2001) identify four key dimensions of integration: structural, cultural, social, and identification. Reflecting on personal experience, one participant describes being thrust into the refugee experience at the age of thirteen, enduring a prolonged and deeply distressing refugee process that was particularly burdensome at such a young age. Understanding the depth and timing of trauma is critical to comprehending refugees' backgrounds, as trauma can occur at any stage of the refugee journey. Consequently, refugees often face multiple and intersecting challenges, with trauma representing one of the most significant obstacles to integration and well-being.

"I feel proud to be Kurdish. I speak five languages fluently and remain politically active regarding my country. I have also written several poems, which I have shared with large Kurdish audiences. I hold three different passports, and I hope that one day, Kurdish people will have their own country again.

All immigrants who have been asylum seekers have suffered in different ways. Our main struggle is that we are not fully recognised as Kurdish, yet we are not entirely European either. It is difficult to find our

place, and as a result, we often struggle to fully belong to any single culture.”

(Gulzar, 38-year-old woman)

Research by Doris and Warriner (2015) demonstrates that language learning plays a significant role in shaping migrants' and refugees' sense of belonging. Ongoing challenges in language acquisition are often closely connected to refugees' educational backgrounds and experiences of displacement and trauma. Little (2019) further highlights the strong emotional connections multilingual individuals form with particular languages, underscoring the affective dimensions of language use in contexts of migration.

Integration is a complex and multidimensional process that extends well beyond language proficiency and employment. Evaluating integration solely through these indicators risks overlooking the diverse and often difficult realities refugees face, including varied educational trajectories, exposure to armed conflict, violations of human rights, discrimination, and political involvement in regions such as Kurdistan, all of which contribute to unequal access to education and opportunities.

A growing body of research emphasises the centrality of belonging to personal health and well-being (Kitchen et al., 2012). Anthias (2006) conceptualises belonging as deeply emotional, rooted in social bonds and interpersonal connections (p. 21). Similarly, Marsh et al. (2007) argue that belonging is closely tied to

social networks and the affirmation of social identity (p. 4). Together, these perspectives highlight belonging as a critical dimension of integration that encompasses emotional, social, and structural elements.

“The environment in which I lived in Kurdistan was completely different from the environment I live in now. Finland is culturally and socially very different from my country of origin. When asylum seekers arrive in Europe, they come with heavy and deeply rooted struggles. Finland is a democratic country where human rights are recognised, people can express their views, and humanity is respected. We grew up in a context where none of these conditions existed. As a result, the cultural shock is profound. The level of freedom people have in Finland is something we have never experienced in our own country.

In my view, first-generation immigrants face significant difficulties when settling into a new culture. Their past experiences and the challenges they have endured have a direct impact on their lives in the host country. While we all need to work harder to integrate and reflect on and change some of our old ways of thinking, Finland also remains a relatively closed society. Other cultures and customs are not always easily accepted or integrated into Finnish society. Although there has been a small increase in the number of immigrants working and becoming integrated, this remains limited to a minority. *(Kamal, 51-year-old man)*

Integration involves enabling refugees and migrants to participate actively alongside native populations, contributing collectively to the development of a cohesive society in the host country. Key dimensions of integration include

cultural knowledge, vocational training, and language proficiency, as highlighted by Koskela (2014, p. 9). In Finland, the Personal Integration Plan defines a structured integration period of three to five years following arrival, during which individuals are entitled to access training programmes and services designed to support their integration process.

Recognising and addressing the impact of refugees' traumatic experiences is equally essential, given the significant emotional, physical, and psychological burdens many have endured. Trauma is often an integral part of the refugee journey, underscoring the need for comprehensive and coordinated support across multiple domains to assist individuals in rebuilding their lives, restoring well-being, and fostering long-term inclusion.

"I became increasingly involved in the community around me and founded a Kurdish association to help Kurdish and Finnish people understand one another better. I visited Finnish schools to introduce students to Kurdish culture and customs, and I organised Kurdish cultural evenings and social events where people could meet, talk, and enjoy time together.

Through these activities, I was able to create meaningful change. I introduced many Kurdish people to Finnish communities, contributed to improved mutual understanding, and helped strengthen relationships between different groups. Our work came to be recognised as important by wider Finnish society.

I believe it is essential for all of us to work together to build a shared community. I have personally supported Kurdish people in adapting to Finnish culture and

navigating the integration process. In my view, integration differs for each individual, but learning the language and understanding the culture are key factors that help people integrate more effectively and feel a genuine sense of belonging." (*Farshad, 46-year-old man*)

The process of integrating into Finnish society can be challenging for refugees and may involve tensions between different ethnic groups, sometimes resulting in experiences of isolation. Creating inclusive spaces that recognise diversity and multiplicity is therefore essential, allowing for the acknowledgement of varied perspectives, emotions, and future aspirations (Parekh, 2000).

Language acquisition plays a central role in the refugee journey (Gillespie et al., 2018). Language education programmes for refugees should be tailored to their specific circumstances, as personal histories, motivations, and life situations strongly influence engagement in language learning (Kleinmann, 1984).

Understanding the background and consequences of refugee trauma is critical for comprehending the broader dynamics of the refugee experience. Many refugees have endured significant physical and psychological trauma throughout the displacement process. Empowering refugee voices and providing appropriate support to address their needs are essential steps toward facilitating meaningful participation and inclusion within integration programmes in Finland.

“Migrants need to make a strong effort to improve their lives in their host countries. Asylum seekers often carry many difficulties from their past experiences. I have learned a great deal since living in Finland, and I can also compare this with my experiences in my country of origin. In Finland, I have encountered many positive values that I had not known before. I have learned to respect people from different backgrounds, with different opinions and identities, regardless of their differences.” (*Zakaria, 47-year-old man*)

Finland seeks to strengthen the role of refugees and migrants in their own integration by promoting labour market participation, including through private-sector investment. However, the country has faced challenges in fully recognising and utilising the employment potential of refugees and migrants. These difficulties are partly linked to social and institutional structures that differ from those in many other OECD countries, which can complicate integration processes (Lindström, 2018).

Refugees’ health outcomes are shaped by multiple and interrelated factors that span past experiences, present living conditions, and future uncertainties. Lifestyle factors, environmental conditions, and the evolving vulnerabilities encountered throughout the refugee journey all have a significant impact on health. For example, experiences among Kurdish refugees indicate that limited general and health literacy—often resulting from disrupted education due to conflict in the Kurdistan region—act as major barriers to accessing health information, services, and essential self-care skills.

“I began studying the language and eventually became fluent enough to manage my own affairs without needing a translator. However, I still did not fully understand all the medical terms in Finnish. Being able to understand my illness in Kurdish helped me to care for myself more effectively.” (*Mansur, 57-year-old man*)

Social integration encompasses the cultural, communal, and personal dimensions of individuals lived experiences (Habermas, 1987). Having grown up under difficult political conditions in the Kurdistan region, he witnessed multiple forms of hardship and came to the conclusion that pursuing a better future required change and relocation. Kurdish migrants often embody multiculturalism as they navigate and negotiate multiple cultural influences in their everyday lives. In this sense, multiculturalism represents not only a social reality but also a significant marker of collective identity and resilience.

However, persistent discrimination, the absence of fundamental human rights, and ongoing political and military conflicts in Kurdistan have severely limited opportunities for education and employment, particularly for younger generations. These structural constraints have compelled many to seek refuge elsewhere. Despite such adversity, many Kurdish migrants demonstrate considerable resilience, energy, and capacity to rebuild their lives in new social and cultural contexts.

“I decided to learn the language so that I could start a new life and find my place in this new society. I

wanted to make a positive change in my own life. Learning a new language also helps individuals access employment opportunities.

I supported other refugees by providing translation and guidance to help them settle in Finland. I also participated in public events and speaking engagements to discuss multiculturalism, intending to help Finnish people better understand migrants and our experiences.”

(Karim, 46-year-old man)

Refugees and migrants occupy particularly vulnerable positions within integration processes, as they must engage directly with diverse individuals and institutions in multiple contexts while forming new relationships essential to social inclusion. Integration, therefore, involves not only adaptation but also the establishment of new roles, identities, and social connections within the host society. Understanding and mobilising integration resources—such as multicultural capital, skills, and lived experiences—can be highly beneficial for refugees, informing their integration pathways while simultaneously enriching cultural diversity within the host community.

Language acquisition represents a fundamental need for refugees, as it enables communication, understanding, and participation within a new environment. Learning the host-country language not only enhances practical interaction but also supports the development of social identity and belonging. Moreover, language learning provides individuals with the means to express emotional and spiritual experiences

that may otherwise remain unarticulated. In this context, one participant described enduring profound emotional pain, which he kept internalised and did not share with family or friends until arriving in the host country. His journey toward healing required rebuilding his life through learning, particularly by mastering the Finnish language. Gaining sufficient language proficiency allowed him to communicate his experiences to a therapist in Finland—an essential step that facilitated his recovery and well-being.

The successful integration of refugees and migrants can generate significant economic, cultural, and social benefits for host countries. Nevertheless, integration remains a highly complex and multifaceted process. Developing a deeper understanding of social integration requires attention to the role of human capital, including skills, education, and social competencies, in shaping integration outcomes.

Refugees often need to negotiate a delicate balance between maintaining elements of their cultural heritage and adapting to the social norms of the host society. This negotiation involves managing cultural continuity while addressing the tensions and conflicts that may arise during processes of cultural adaptation (Valtonen, 1990).

Language plays a pivotal role in empowering refugees within their social environments. It functions not only as a means of communication but also as a tool for self-empowerment,

influencing individuals' capacity to integrate, participate, and develop a meaningful sense of belonging within their new communities.

The Role of Education in the Refugee Experience

Kurdistan is widely characterised as a deeply patriarchal society, in which cultural, economic, historical, and political barriers frequently restrict women's access to education and positions of power. As a result of these structural inequalities, many women encounter significant obstacles in securing educational opportunities. The importance of learning one's mother tongue cannot be overstated, as it serves as a key marker of identity, enabling individuals to connect with their past, navigate their present, and imagine their future. As Maalouf (2016, p. 19) aptly observes, "Language serves as the axis of cultural identity, while the diversity of languages represents the axis of all diversities."

In addition, education plays a crucial role in transmitting the values, norms, and social practices of the host country. Bodwig (2015) emphasises that access to education is fundamental to facilitating successful integration, as it supports both individual empowerment and meaningful participation in the host society.

"I was not able to go to school

I wasn't able to read or write

I wasn't able to study

I never got a chance to learn

I never learned to read or write.

I tried to study again

I wasn't able to concentrate enough to learn"

(Narenj, 60-year-old female)

Education plays a central role in the integration of migrants, offering multiple and interconnected benefits. First, it helps alleviate concerns related to economic stability by enhancing employability and skills. Second, education expands knowledge and strengthens individuals' ability to interpret and critically engage with information, supporting a more balanced and secure life. Research in migration and refugee studies consistently demonstrates that education fosters more positive attitudes toward migrants and serves as a crucial mechanism for integration. De Paola and Brunello (2016) underscore this point, noting that "education transmits norms of tolerance and equality, fostering humanitarian and egalitarian sentiments among the native population, countering cultural and racial prejudices."

The quality of education is equally important in upholding the fundamental right to education. Access to educational opportunities varies significantly across regions, and substantial gender disparities persist. According to the UNHCR (2011), girls worldwide face greater barriers to education than boys, highlighting the role of education in facilitating social integration and equity for refugee populations in host countries. The UNHCR further emphasises-

es that education not only fulfils basic learning needs but also enriches learners' overall quality of life.

Within refugee communities, education holds particular significance as it provides individuals with a voice and symbolises aspirations for freedom and self-determination (INEE, 2010, p. 9). In the Kurdistan region, ongoing military conflict has forced many children to leave school prematurely. In this context, education remains a cornerstone for building a more just world, offering meaningful opportunities to improve life circumstances and foster long-term resilience.

"I was able to attend school

I graduated with good grades

I never gave up on studying

I did not understand the written text

I learned the language

I learned to understand

I began attending the Finnish language

I decided to study further

I would study in the mornings and in the evenings

I started to be interested in becoming a beautician

I graduated as a beautician"

(Shno, 38 years old female)

Past trauma experienced by refugees has a profound impact on both physical and emo-

tional well-being. Research on migrants' health literacy, such as the study by Lee and Kang (2018), demonstrates that language proficiency, educational attainment, age, and gender play critical roles in shaping health literacy within migration and refugee contexts. Understanding the influence of education and literacy on refugees' capacity to navigate health systems and succeed in host countries is therefore essential.

Singleton and Krause (2009) found that individuals with lower levels of literacy often struggle to understand medical information in the host-country language, which can negatively affect health outcomes. Importantly, health literacy in one's native language does not automatically translate into proficiency in the language of the host country, creating additional barriers to effective healthcare access. UNESCO (2000, Article 8) highlights the responsibility of education systems to respond to conflict, crises, and instability, while promoting mutual understanding, peace, and tolerance, and contributing to the prevention of violence and conflict.

I ran in the dark

I fell into the (Tenor)oven.

My face, chest and hands were all burned

I would never forget

I learned to adopt

I was good at school

I kept studying

I was trying to replace

I was one of the best students

I felt like the other students

I decided to start handwriting

I wasn't able to study

I didn't make

I had to stop studying

I really wanted to study

I loved the arts

I really wanted to study again

(Peshava, 40-year-old male)

Access to education is a fundamental human right and a vital instrument for strengthening the cultural and social identity of refugees within host societies. Nicolai and Triplehorn (2003) emphasise that education provides multiple forms of protection, including *psychosocial protection*, which supports emotional and psychological well-being, and *cognitive protection*, which promotes learning and personal development. In addition, Gosling (2000) highlights that refugees often conceptualise health holistically, encompassing both emotional and physical dimensions of well-being. I decided not to continue my studies

I did not enjoy it

I did not feel motivated to continue

I moved to the north of Finland

I started learning

I felt free and reborn

I was very eager to learn

I knew

I had learned was not enough

I attended a course

I was expected to start

I studied

I tried to learn alone

I had to stand with"

(Mahabad, 40-year-old female)

Women's education is widely recognised as a powerful form of empowerment, enabling women to challenge traditional roles and respond to demands for social change (Alagarsamy, 2018). As hooks (2000) argues, education provides a pathway for individuals to realise their full potential and promotes greater equality within societies. Across European countries, the integration of migrants presents ongoing challenges, with education playing a pivotal role in supporting inclusion and participation in new communities.

In the context of military conflict in Kurdistan, the right to education—including basic health, safety, and well-being education—has frequently been disrupted or denied. Kurdish individuals have often been deprived of opportuni-

ties to study their mother tongue within formal education systems. According to UNICEF (2000), education is a cornerstone of poverty reduction and social development; however, in environments characterised by fear and instability, many children are forced to leave school at an early age. A significant number of these children experience lasting physical and psychological trauma. Graça (2000) highlights that children affected by conflict have distinct and complex needs due to the harm caused by their traumatic experiences. Furthermore, research by Schock et al., (2016) underscores that refugees, as a result of prolonged exposure to trauma, are particularly vulnerable to secondary traumatic stress.

I began school at the age of seven.

I attended school until secondary school

I went to school during the revolution

I did not feel like going to school

I wasn't able to finish school

I started attending a language

I wasn't able to study

I was able to learn the language.

I have learned to accept

(Kaveh, 49-year-old male)

Pre-migration experiences such as exposure to violence, political conflict, and trauma are strongly associated with an increased risk of mental health disorders among refugees

(Georgiadou et al., 2017). Research conducted in countries such as Australia and Austria further demonstrates that acculturative stress, alongside the migration process itself, significantly contributes to these mental health challenges (Kartal & Kiropoulos, 2016). Consequently, integration into a new cultural context should aim to preserve individuals' core cultural identities while taking into account the perspectives and needs of both refugees and host societies (Kartal & Kiropoulos, 2016).

I was a good student

I experienced a lot of bad things

I experienced

I graduated

I had made a promise

I could make it through

I would go and study again

I really wanted to do

I wanted to study sociology

I could study on the side

I could not study

(Mustafa, 47-year-old male)

Research has identified homesickness as a critical dimension of refugees' experiences in host societies. Papadopoulos (2002) conceptualises homesickness as a "deep sense of nostalgic yearning for the restoration of a specific loss." To support gradual and sustainable

integration, refugees require access to knowledge and educational resources that help bridge gaps between their past experiences and new social environments. Migration introduces complex challenges related to the transmission of values and the adaptation to new social roles (Binder & Tošić, 2005). The OECD (2019) further emphasises that successful refugee integration can strengthen social capacity, reduce tensions between refugees and host societies, and promote greater equality within communities.

I went to school for eight years

I had to drop out

I had always wanted to move

I managed to learn the language

I slowly learned to speak the language

I had studied English in Syria

I loved studying

I chose sociology

I really enjoyed school

I wasn't fluent in the Finnish language

I managed to learn to speak Finnish

I think learning a new language

I learned to speak Finnish

I can speak five languages

I've also studied a little bit of music

(Gulzar, 38-year-old female)

According to the international legal definition set out in the 1951 Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees and its 1967 Protocol, refugees are individuals who, "owing to a well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group, or political opinion, are outside the country of their nationality and are unable or, owing to such fear, unwilling to avail themselves of the protection of that country" (UN General Assembly, 1951). Displacement from their countries of origin occurs for a range of interrelated reasons, often involving perilous journeys across multiple countries (Enloe, 1990).

In seeking safety and a viable future, refugees frequently recognise education as a vital resource for navigating the complex challenges encountered throughout displacement and resettlement. This is particularly significant given that many refugees have experienced disrupted or limited access to schooling due to conflict, persecution, or instability in their home countries. Education, fundamentally, constitutes a basic human right and plays a critical role in supporting protection, resilience, and long-term integration.

I have studied until primary school

I had to stop going to school

I got involved

I moved to Finland

I am still politically active

I try to help my people

I hope to see a change

I hope that one day Finland

I think Finnish people see us as migrants

(Kamal, 51-year-old male)

Experienced trauma has a profound and lasting impact on individuals' mental health and well-being, often extending across generations (Bezo & Maggie, 2015). A Swedish study reported notably high levels of trauma-related symptoms within refugee families (Daud et al., 2008). Further research demonstrates that parental trauma among refugees is strongly associated with adverse psychological outcomes in their children (Vaage et al., 2011). In particular, maternal trauma has been shown to significantly affect adolescents' mental health, contributing to emotional distress and behavioural difficulties. These enduring effects of trauma disrupt both the internal psychological world and the external social realities of refugees (Steel et al., 2006).

Refugee families face multiple and intersecting challenges and often require access to education as a key resource for mitigating difficulties in everyday life. Handlin (1951) conceptualises refugees as displaced individuals who experience losses across all spheres of life, including social identity, livelihoods, place, family, friendships, and support networks. Their struggle in-

volves adapting to a new culture and society, frequently within unfamiliar linguistic and cultural environments, while attempting to rebuild stability and meaning in their lives.

I completed high school in Baghdad

I wasn't able to graduate

I had to drop out

I began a new journey in Finland

I began learning the Finnish language

I then joined a college

I began studying again

I studied hard

I wasn't guided throughout

I was treated similarly to Finnish students

I noticed a journalism course

I was really interested in

I am quite talented

I can speak multiple languages

I decided to go back to school

I graduated

I started a Kurdish association to help the Kurdish

I would go around Finnish schools

(Farshad, 45-year-old male)

Research on refugees from Iran indicates that all participants in one study were diagnosed with post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD),

with particularly heightened avoidance behaviours following significant life events (Schock et al., 2016). Kunz (1973, 1981) categorises refugee movements into two primary models: anticipatory movements and acute movements resulting from conflict. When mental health needs remain untreated, migrants may experience prolonged suffering, with negative consequences for education, employment, and family life (Nguï et al., 2010).

Refugees frequently endure traumatic experiences such as violence and torture, which can lead to increased somatic symptoms and chronic pain disorders. Findings from the Finnish Migrant Health and Wellbeing Study (Maamu) reveal those Kurdish migrants, in particular, experience elevated levels of mental health difficulties, including symptoms of anxiety and depression (Rask et al., 2015). Research on migration further highlights the complex and layered nature of belonging, which often involves multiple and simultaneous attachments to place, resulting in what has been described as a “multi-sited” sense of belonging (Bennett, 2014; Marcu, 2014).

Belonging within a community is closely linked to processes of self-identification shaped by past experiences. Yuval-Davis (2006) conceptualises belonging as a “feeling at home,” emphasising its emotional, relational, and contextual dimensions.

I lived in that village until primary school

I have a sad memory

We can all speak Farsi

What do we tell our parents?

I was stuttering, but

I still wanted to answer

I put my hand up and wanted to answer

I said, “

I go home and say Slaw dayika

I barely finished my sentence when he hit my head with a large stick several times.

You must say it in Farsi,

I did not want to continue studying

I decided to join the Young Union Association

(Zakaria, 50-year-old male)

Kurdish migrants are often exposed to high levels of traumatic events, which are associated with elevated rates of depression, anxiety, and somatic symptoms, as well as experiences of discrimination and additional stressors in host societies. Miller et al. (2008) discuss the complex and sometimes conflicting findings regarding the relative significance of pre- and post-migration factors, highlighting their combined influence on mental health and overall well-being.

Studies conducted in Finland further indicate that many Kurdish migrants have experienced threats and harassment in their countries of origin. These traumatic experiences frequently manifest in host contexts as high levels of

trauma-related disorders, including chronic pain and somatic symptoms.

I studied until fifth grade

I had a normal life

I then realised

I was a Kurd

I had a responsibility

I was ready to become a Peshmerga

I was young

I was in danger

I moved to Finland

I began studying the language

I learned to speak

I was fluent enough

I studied to become an electrician

I stopped studying

(Mansur, 47-year-old male)

Migration is a multifaceted process encompassing pre-migration, migration, and post-migration phases, each of which plays a significant role in shaping the refugee experience. In 2018, the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) reported a record 68.5 million forcibly displaced individuals worldwide, including 25.4 million refugees. This unprece-

ented level of forced displacement constitutes a major global public health challenge.

Research conducted in Sweden found that 81% of Kurdish men experienced discrimination, which was strongly associated with mental health symptoms and a reduced quality of life (Taloyan et al., 2006). Similarly, studies in Finland indicate a pressing need for enhanced mental health interventions among Kurdish migrants (Rask et al., 2015). Broader research further demonstrates a clear and consistent relationship between experiences of discrimination and psychological well-being (Castaneda et al., 2015).

Refugees' social recovery is closely intertwined with the trauma endured throughout the displacement process, which is often characterised by experiences of humiliation, loss, and persecution. Traumatized refugees face the demanding task of rebuilding their lives and communities from the ground up, requiring strong social capacities and support systems to navigate and thrive within new societal and cultural contexts (Westoby & Ingamells, 2010).

I learned to read the Koran

I was very good at reading

I began grade one

I Rape with

I swore to myself

I decided to keep

I was always politically active

I really enjoyed studying
I studied really well
I participated in various competitions
I would always get a really good grade
I got 120 points from
I was able to memorise all of the Quran
I was really interested in the Kurdish language
I was also able to read
I loved reading books
I was very keen on comedy
I will become the next Charlie Chaplin
I studied acting
I was very happy
I really enjoyed
I also really enjoyed history and geography
I stayed in the mountains
I was only 15 years old
I learnt fast and quickly
I became one of the best students
I was really sad
I used to read books
I was always scared to read
I would go to a graveyard to read books
I enjoyed

I moved to Finland.
I tried to learn the language
I developed a very good social network
I learned to speak the language
I request to see a therapist
I did not feel safe
I applied to study at a university
I applied to study politics
(Hemin, 46-year-old male)

Culturalization in Refugee Experience

The Kurds constitute the largest population in the Middle East without an independent state and have long sought recognition of their right to self-determination. Their culture has been shaped and transformed through dispersion across four nation-states, resulting in diverse social, political, and cultural expressions (Philip & Christine, 1996). Many participants in this study have histories of political engagement, reflecting the unresolved Kurdish question, which has led to widespread experiences of displacement, imprisonment, execution, and martyrdom among Kurdish communities.

Yavuz (1998) argues that Kurdish culture predates the emergence of Kurdish nationalism, underscoring the depth and historical continuity of Kurdish identity. According to estimates by the Kurdish Institute of Paris (2017), the Kurd-

ish population ranges between 36.4 and 45.6 million people, residing across four states as well as throughout the global diaspora.

Understanding diverse human needs across cultural contexts is essential, particularly in migration and refugee settings. Refugees often struggle with processes of cultural adaptation and integration in host societies, encountering challenges that arise from social, cultural, and structural differences. These processes of adaptation are shaped by both individual experiences and broader societal dynamics, highlighting the importance of culturally informed approaches to integration and support.

“Shno fled her home country was very young. She was forced to leave her family support and friends behind. She felt distressed and alone. She learned a new language, and culture, and educated herself and started to work around human rights and helping Kurdish women”.

Migrants entering a new society are often expected to adapt to its social norms, including practices related to work ethics, hygiene standards, traffic regulations, and broader codes of conduct. While fear and uncertainty may silence expressions of distress associated with these expectations, many women today actively challenge such constraints by pursuing human freedom and rights. The concept of *culturalisation* refers to an integrated process that encompasses the multiple forms and dimensions of culture within the context of the host

society, emphasising adaptation while recognising cultural diversity (Young, 2008).

“Peshava fled to Turkey because of his political activities and the fear that the government would torture him and his family. However, their asylum-seeking journey was very hard, and it had a very long-lasting impact on him. While he tried to adapt to the new culture and society, he was unable to forget his past. Eventually, he learned the language and got into a political community to give the Kurdish nation a voice. He describes his painful past as a bright light because it taught him to believe in his own power”

Experience in navigating multicultural environments is increasingly essential, given the widespread multicultural character of contemporary societies. Developing an understanding of cultural differences is vital, and the concept of *culturalisation* involves constructing informed and responsive approaches to multiculturalism. Lefebvre et al., (1992) conceptualise culture as expressed through multiple forms, including geography, society, and history. Culturalisation can therefore be understood as the application of a comprehensive and contemporary understanding of culture, encompassing both the diversity and everyday practices of life within a society. This form

of cultural preparation creates opportunities for deeper and more meaningful integration into new cultural and social contexts (Young, 2008).

Her narrative offers insights from multiple perspectives, incorporating a multicultural standpoint while also illuminating issues related to women's rights, particularly in light of the violations she experienced. The story further reflects her depth of knowledge, critical awareness, and capacity to engage thoughtfully with these complex and pressing concerns.

“Mahabad said she never planned to leave her home country one day. After getting married, she left her hometown with her husband for a better life by paying smugglers to transport them to another country. While they managed to leave Iran, they had several bad experiences in Russia, Turkey and Iraq, including deportation. She and her husband were finally accepted as asylum seekers in Finland, but at that time, she was accepted first, so she came to the country alone, and her husband joined her a few months later. She has also experienced abuse in her marriage and was very broken and hurt. She eventually got a divorce and married again sometime later. Her new husband helped her to heal and forget her past. She felt empowered and decided to learn the language, study, and learn a profession and get a job. She now has her own

business. She also has two children and lives a quiet and normal life in Finland”.

Culturalisation can be understood as a powerful strategy for addressing the specific needs of a culture through a cohesive and contextual interpretation of its constituent elements. I challenge the prevailing approaches adopted by international organisations toward the implementation of cultural integration, arguing that these frameworks often fail to reflect lived realities. This disconnect represents one of the key challenges in translating integration policies into effective practice (Young, 2008).

“Kamran, at the age of 15, joined DPK (Democrat Party of Kurdistan). After many years of work, he moved to the Iraqi Kurdistan region and got married at the age of 20. Because of the harsh conditions of the region, he decided to move to Turkey as an asylum seeker. He says that his experience in Turkey was very hard and stressful, and he often prayed to soon move into a new country. The United Nations finally permitted him to move to Finland. In Kamran's experience, Finland was the opposite of Iran in every way, from the climate to the culture and the people. He tried hard to integrate into the new culture by learning the language. He also worked hard to earn money and sent most of it back to his family in Iran. He now has his own business, and his time is divided between work responsibilities and his family. He has more time and freedom to spend with his family and friends now.”

According to Huntington (1997), processes of culturalisation are often framed through the dominant narrative of a “clash of cultures,” highlighting the increasing salience of culture in social and political discourse. This contemporary phenomenon, as discussed by Tonkens and Duyvendak (2016), reflects the emergence of a new form of nationalism that places growing emphasis on rules, values, symbols, customs, and reconfigured notions of identification and belonging over recent decades.

“Kaveh dropped out of school because of the irregular school schedules in the unsafe Kurdistan Region. When Kaveh was very young, he joined the Peshmerga group but got injured several times in the wars. However, according to his words, his wounds would heal very quickly. He was seriously injured and lost one of his legs. This affected him mentally, more so because it limited his physical activity. The lack of doctors and medication, as well as the unsafety in Kurdistan, and the loss of many of his friends, forced him to seek a better life. He introduced himself to the UN in Iraqi Kurdistan. The UN sent him and his family as asylum seekers to Finland. In Finland, he faced severe depression and needed treatment for a very long time. His past made him sad, and seeing his old photo albums often made him sad. He tried very hard to forget the past by learning the Finnish language and getting a job, but it didn't work out. Because of severe pain and prolonged sick leave, he retired at a very young age. The doctors in Finland made him an artificial leg. He has now lived in Finland for

twenty years. He learnt the language and has many friends. His physical body pain is still there, and it is discomforting. But his deepest wish is to return to Kurdistan one day.”

The concept of culture encompasses the ways in which lives and everyday practices are integrated into society, highlighting a shift from a singular “way of life” to multiple and diverse “ways of life” within new cultural contexts. This understanding views culture as encompassing the totality of social existence, including language, belief systems, and dimensions of health and well-being (Jary & Jary, 1991, p. 138). The notion of culture as a “way of life,” introduced by Williams in the 1950s, has been foundational in shaping contemporary cultural analysis. Building on this perspective, Jameson (1984) identifies the emergence of new cultural forms and their consequences, marking the development of a process often described as *culturalisation*, which has evolved since the 1970s.

Recognising and understanding the diverse cultural identities and affiliations of refugees is essential for interpreting their mental health experiences. The complexity of these varied backgrounds can generate multiple challenges, including exposure to trauma, experiences of discrimination and racism, and issues related to disability, all of which shape refugees' well-being and integration trajectories.

“Mustafa was born into a family with a political background. His childhood coincided with the Is-

Islamic Revolution of Iran. He has had military conflict experience in his childhood. He said that the conditions of that time introduced him to the concept of the Peshmerga and the gun. He had seen many bitter experiences in his life, such as the killing of innocent people and children being prevented from studying in the Kurdistan region for various reasons. He decided at that time that if he grew up, he would help people get their rights. The Kurdish students need higher education to continue to go through security checks. He was a good grad student, but due to the security check, he couldn't continue his studies. He was imprisoned for seven years. Life and political activity had become very difficult for him, and so his wife and he decided to leave their country and place of residence and move to Turkey. They escaped to Turkey by paying a high price to the smuggler. Living in Turkey was very difficult because of unemployment, financial problems, uncertain conditions, and the constant fear of being deported. He said he lost all his human ability there. He promised himself that he would study in the future because he was interested in sociology. But to pay the debt in Turkey, he needed to work hard in Finland, and unfortunately, he couldn't study. He started a new life, started working and got integrated into this new country via social networks and friendship, facing to go through trauma background consequence."

Gordon and Mundy (2001, p. 5) argue that "culture serves as the foundation of development," highlighting the importance of adopting a com-

prehensive and culturally informed approach to policy. Cultural positioning can create opportunities to enhance integration within new social environments by recognising and mobilising the capacities inherent within different cultures. This process enables the articulation of categories, relationships, and boundaries through which individuals and groups make sense of their social worlds.

Integrating culture into a new societal framework, therefore, represents a significant challenge and lies at the heart of the cultural transition commonly described as *culturalisation*. Culturalisation constitutes a crucial dimension of cultural interpretation, fostering the emergence of new cultural forms grounded in respect for diversity, inclusion, and human rights.

"At the age of thirteen, Gulzar experienced a refugee process path at the request of his older brother, who lived in Sweden. For a better life and a better future, because life in Syria was no longer safe and secure, she decided to leave Syria for Sweden, which was not easy. She has had many unpleasant experiences, including being imprisoned during travel, walking a lot, sleeping in unfamiliar places, getting acquainted with human smugglers, feeling lonely, missing her mother, and crossing different countries. Two of her siblings accompanied her, who were several years older than her. As they were underage and had no previous experience, when they arrived in Sweden, they were settled in the children's home. She learned the language and started to study, and she chose sociology. The re-

sult of this marriage is two children, one boy and one girl. Eight years later, we separated. Now my son lives with my daughter, with her father. I'm still in Finland because of my kids. I'm for the release of loneliness, trying to write a poem, reading a book and listening to music. Gulzar can speak several languages, and she is working on translation in Finland. She wishes that one day to have her own country, a free Kurdistan.”

Social Capital Competencies in Refugee Experience

The pivotal role of social capital in the experiences and integration of Kurdish refugees is evident in their journeys toward belonging and community inclusion. To illustrate this, I draw on three examples of successfully integrated Kurdish refugees who serve as guides and role models within their communities.

Social capital represents a critical dimension of the refugee experience, encompassing language proficiency, educational skills, acculturation processes, social relationships, and access to diverse social networks (Cheung & Phillimore, 2013). Putnam (2000) argues that a decline in social capital undermines both quality of life and community vitality. Accordingly, social capital comprises social groups, interpersonal ties, shared identities, norms, values, trust, cooperation, and reciprocity. Putnam et al. (2000) further emphasise its importance in sustaining democratic societies and highlight

its dual functions of *bonding* within groups and *bridging* across diverse social networks.

In contemporary contexts, social capital increasingly extends to online spaces, such as social media platforms, contributing to the formation of “virtual” social capital (Ellison et al., 2007). These digital networks facilitate altruism, mutual support, and information sharing, and are closely linked to health, welfare, and well-being. Personal sociability also remains deeply connected to kinship and friendship networks (Putnam, 2000, p. 19).

Bourdieu (1972) conceptualises social networks as a vital bridge between refugee populations and the wider society, enabling access to valuable social capital resources. For refugees, meaningful friendships and participation in diverse networks have been shown to positively influence integration and acculturation in host countries (Cheung & Phillimore, 2013). Foley and Edwards (1998) similarly emphasise that social capital is collectively generated through networks rather than existing solely at the individual level.

An illustrative example can be found in the story of a Kurdish refugee featured in a Finnish newspaper (*Ilta-Sanomat*, 2020), which highlighted sustained efforts to build strong relationships with Finnish residents. Such initiatives exemplify how the mobilisation of social capital can support integration and foster a deeper sense of belonging in the host society.

Putnam (2000) also draws attention to the evolving nature of social connections over the past century, reflecting changes in both informal and formal communication competencies. Social capital thus assumes varied meanings and values across societies, shaped by how social groups understand and practise norms, trust, cooperation, and reciprocity. Portes (1998) further conceptualises social capital as a key resource for problem-solving, reinforcing the central idea that “social networks have value” (Putnam, 2000, p. 206).

Likewise, Shno, another participant, described the disparity between her native country and the social connections she encountered in Finland. Here is an excerpt from her life story, as shared with me:

“In our culture in Iran, neighbours take care of each other when needed. Her reaction made me realise how different our cultures were. I learnt that Finnish culture was the complete opposite of ours. It made me feel very lonely and isolated.”

Similarly, another participant, Kamal, explained the change in the surrounding environment. The following shows her life story experiences in a quote formed from her experience shared with me.

“The environment I lived in Kurdistan is completely different to the environment I live in now. Finland is culturally and socially very different to where I come from. When asylum seekers come to Europe,

they are very different people with heavy and deep struggles.”

Putnam (1995, p. 77) examined the impact of technology on social connections, suggesting that media such as television and the Internet increasingly contribute to the “individualisation” of social life. He further speculated that future technological developments, including immersive technologies such as “virtual reality helmets,” could intensify social isolation, potentially widening the divide between individual and collective interests and undermining social equality.

Within the Finnish context, the Kurdish community actively seeks to improve both their own living conditions and those of others by drawing on competencies related to belonging, community, and integration. Central to these efforts is their ability to build and sustain social networks and relationships—commonly conceptualised as social capital. Bourdieu (1972) distinguishes multiple forms of social capital, including economic, social, and symbolic dimensions. Reflecting this perspective, Farshad, a participant in the life story research, emphasised the importance of collaboration between Kurds and Finns in strengthening social networks and fostering meaningful relationships. He emphasised this in the following excerpt from his story:

“I started to get more involved with the community around me. I started a Kurdish association to help Kurdish and Finnish people to know and under-

stand each other better. I would go around Finnish schools to introduce and educate Finnish students about Kurdish culture and customs. I would also arrange Kurdish evening events and parties where people could talk to each other and have a good time together.”

According to Hanifan (1916), social capital encompasses everyday interactions such as friendship, empathy, shared purpose, and neighbourly communication. These forms of social engagement contribute significantly to improving quality of life by fostering a sense of belonging, community, and integration. Putnam (1993) further emphasised the potential of social capital as a valuable resource for addressing common social challenges in contemporary societies, including crime and social disconnection.

During a life story interview, Kamal reflected on the evolving political landscape and regulatory frameworks in relation to the development of social capital within a new community. He expressed optimism that the second generation would encounter fewer obstacles than the first. An excerpt from his narrative is presented below.

“The first generation of migrants will have a lot of problems when settling into a new culture. Their past and the issues they’ve dealt with will have a direct impact on their new life. It is much easier for the second generation to cope and settle down in a new country. Growing up in a country where they can learn the language early on will have a big positive

impact on their life. They are not a victim of their memories and past lives....”

The concept of social capital is closely connected to the ways in which refugees integrate into new communities. During resettlement, refugees and migrants actively seek information and knowledge to build trust and establish meaningful relationships within their new social environments. Smith and Baltes (1997) argue that inclusion and a sense of belonging within social networks can offer significant benefits for refugees’ well-being and integration. Similarly, Griffiths et al., (2005) emphasise the importance of fostering connections and trust-based relationships across different groups and communities as a key component of successful integration.

Dasgupta (2002) conceptualises social capital as comprising social norms and network connections that enhance societal efficiency. The development of human capital—particularly through education and health—also contributes positively to the growth and sustainability of social capital. Furthermore, Putnam (2000) highlights an intrinsic relationship between social movements and social capital, noting that the formation of social networks expands resources for both collective action and community engagement.

Conclusion

Kurdish refugees have often endured profoundly distressing experiences that compelled

them to flee their homeland. Before displacement, many were exposed to imprisonment, torture, malnutrition, physical assault, extreme fear, and, in some cases, sexual violence. Their journeys as asylum seekers were frequently marked by separation from family members and close friends, as well as prolonged exposure to harsh and inhospitable living conditions.

Adapting to a new society and culture is neither automatic nor uniform. Achieving a sense of belonging, community, and integration depends on a range of structural and social factors within the host society, including access to resources, education, and relevant knowledge. Among Kurdish refugees, prior experiences and accumulated knowledge have played a significant role in shaping their ability to navigate and integrate into new social and cultural contexts.

Kurdish migrants are often exposed to exceptionally high levels of traumatic events, which are associated with elevated rates of depressive, anxiety, and somatic symptoms, alongside experiences of discrimination and additional post-migration stressors. Miller et al. (2008) highlight the complex and sometimes conflicting evidence regarding the relative influence of pre- and post-migration factors, emphasising their combined impact on mental health and overall well-being. Studies conducted in Finland further indicate that many Kurdish migrants experienced threats and harassment in their countries of origin, with such trauma

frequently manifesting in host societies as chronic pain and other trauma-related somatic conditions.

Language plays a central role in personal identity and social participation, enabling individuals to express emotions, share experiences, and transmit knowledge. Imberti (2007) underscores language as the primary medium through which understanding and communication are achieved, making it a critical element in refugees' integration and well-being.

Research focusing on refugees from Iran demonstrates that individuals diagnosed with post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), particularly those exhibiting avoidance symptoms, may experience heightened avoidance behaviours following new and significant life events (Schock et al., 2016). The post-migration phase introduces additional challenges linked to acculturation, a process that involves adapting to the host culture while simultaneously maintaining connections to one's original cultural identity (Berry, 1997).

Understanding concepts such as belonging, community, and integration requires close engagement with refugees' life narratives. Belonging plays a pivotal role in shaping individuals' lives, signifying the experience of feeling part of—rather than excluded from—an ethnic or social group (Ahmed, 2015, p. 54). Ahmad (2007) similarly emphasises that belonging is central to the meaning individuals assign to their lives. Despite their frequent use, the con-

cepts of belonging and identity remain under-explored within the context of population movements and forced migration (Anthias, 2006, p. 19).

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